

PROMOTING WORK TEAM COHESION THROUGH KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT: A PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract: For millennia, teamwork has been fundamental to human progress, and it has been the focus of social psychology study into small group behaviour for almost 60 years. However, as businesses throughout the world reorganized work around teams during the previous two decades, the nature of cooperation and the variables influencing it became a focus of research in organizational culture and management. This article discusses knowledge management as one of an organization's most significant assets on team cohesion. Hence it may be used to add value to employees, adapt to environmental change, achieve corporate excellence, save time, raise productivity, improve company capacity for innovation, and help management handle employee and customer concerns. The study was founded on qualitative research with three objectives discussed. The study findings established a relationship between variables and demonstrated the impact knowledge resource has on teamwork cohesion in organizations.

Keywords: Knowledge management, work team cohesion, organizational learning, knowledge sharing, knowledge capital

Background

Firms must adapt and deploy their potential to successfully confront market difficulties in today's environment, which is always changing. Knowledge management (KM) is an important aspect of organizational development and work-team collaboration. It incorporates and maintains continual competitive dynamics inside the firm, which regards knowledge as the fundamental potential for increasing production (Jokanovic', Zivlak, Okanovic, Ulibrk, and Dud, 2020). Organizations commonly employ knowledge management for data, information, and knowledge. KM is one of an organization's most valuable assets, as it can be used to create value for customers, respond to environmental change, achieve corporate excellence, save time, increase productivity, improve business capacity for innovation, and enable management to solve employee and customer problems (Tahseen and Ibrahim, 2020). The goal of knowledge management is to create an atmosphere in which strategic managers and workers are encouraged to produce, store, learn, share, and apply explicit and tacit knowledge collaboratively for the benefit of their businesses (Tahseen and Ibrahim, 2020). Since the 1990s, the economy has seen the introduction of new markets and technological advancements (Helder de Jesus and Paulo, 2020). Organizational learning originated

in the realm of business sciences and research, and it has been an important study issue since the 1990s (Helder de Jesus and Paulo, 2020). An organization that continuously increases its capabilities shapes its future. Learning must be led and incorporated into the organization's processes, practices, and structures so that it may be shared and cause performance improvements.

Knowledge management presents a key instrument in enabling organisations to face critical challenges of the adaptation, existence, and competitiveness in the world of growingly incoherent change of the business environment (Agyeiwaah, McKercher and Suntikul, 2017; Yiu and Law, 2014). Developing an organisational culture that values knowledge sharing and knowledge creation can assist in the process of transforming individual or tacit knowledge into collective knowledge (Barišić, Rybacka and Miloloža, 2020). Strong connections among people in a company are essential for effectively generating and creating new information, particularly tacit knowledge (Barišić, Rybacka, & Miloloža, 2020). When people initially join a team or start working for their company, they have difficulty forming new relationships and fostering cohesiveness due to diversity concerns. Kifordu, (2014). To foster cohesiveness among their colleagues or workgroups, they begin to put themselves out there to develop relationships. To promote interpersonal interaction and social interactions, KM approaches must pay special attention to tacit knowledge and investigate novel organizational forms, cultures, and incentive packages (Yiu and Law, 2014; Tribe and Liburd, 2016). Knowledge is an increasingly recognized organizational resource that aids in strategic, tactical, and operational planning (Dereje, 2020). So, it may be defined as an organization's power.

As a result, knowledge must be generated, kept, and maintained to keep any benefits gained from it. According to Kulkarni, Barat, Clark, and Barn, (2015), knowledge management is primarily concerned with creating, providing, empowering, and supporting reasonable learning conditions within an organization to inspire and empower skilled personnel to use and distribute their insight and create new knowledge. Every human power needs information and a method of carrying out actions, which they will get from their peers, teams, and leaders (Dost, Yuosre, Ali, & Tariq, 2016). In today's competitive economic world, information is an organization's most important asset. They will pay since a company's competitiveness is achieved by human resource knowledge, talent, and effort ((Dost, Yuosre, Ali, & Tariq).

Study Concerns

There are significant hurdles in the field of organizational sciences, where yesterday's organizational knowledge and practices cannot ensure future success. Organizational difficulties demand learning and innovation to expand resources, skills, and learning in business organizations in order to maintain the company's competitive edge. Knowledge sharing takes time, and as a result, specialists in specific subjects may be unwilling to engage because some organizations do not compensate them. Different organizations use distinct KM techniques to develop unique capabilities and assure progress toward improved performance. However, some companies are still following traditional business models thereby compromising on change and innovation. The debate over the impact of knowledge management in organizations has become more complex during the past decade because of the nature of how knowledge application is done daily. Knowledge management in each organization has also become complex due to continuous progress in technological advances and inventions and their implications for the workplace. One of the challenges of knowledge management is the failure to form and develop a culture that embraces learning, sharing, changing, and improving knowledge in an organization.

Objectives of the Study

- Ascertain the influence of organizational learning on work-team cohesion.
- Determine the influence of knowledge sharing on work-team cohesion.
- Evaluate the place of knowledge application on work-team cohesion.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Knowledge Management

The review of literature and the analysis of existing views of KM showed that some KM perceptions are technology-based, while most definitions indicate that KM includes assets, activities, or processes for developing and using knowledge to achieve or improve business metrics. These metrics can be organizational goals, values, long-term performance, and overall success. Knowledge itself can be broken into two main categories (Goddard, 2020). Explicit knowledge is that which has been formalized and may be used instantly. Implicit knowledge is generally more difficult to capture and might be referred to as staff "know-how". While implicit knowledge is more difficult to define and quantify, it is an essential component of any company's success since it keeps the organization on track by ensuring seamless functioning in day-to-day activities. It is vital to highlight that the possession of knowledge does not always lead to creativity. The knowledge within an organization must be operationalized to contribute to change and innovation. Subsequently, the generation, capture, and codification of knowledge allow for innovation within an organization only when it is managed and disseminated correctly (Goddard, 2020). With that focus in mind, it becomes important to define how KM is used and applied in a broad sense. Agarwal and Island (2014) posited that knowledge management is operationalized in three distinct phases that form the KM cycle. The first phase is knowledge capture/creation, which defines the knowledge within the organization. The second phase is knowledge sharing and transfer, during which the knowledge that was previously captured is made available to others for use in the workplace, Kifordu., Ogbo and Ukpere, (2014). The creation of a foundation of knowledge and making that knowledge accessible to the required users within the organization are the first steps in successful integration. Finally, the third phase is knowledge application and use. From there, the KMS can be used as a tool to inspire innovation within the organization by ensuring that lessons learned in the past are captured and that past experiences can help the organization grow. Knowledge management (KM) is the process of producing, gathering, sharing, and using knowledge to improve organizational performance. Tahseen and Ibrahim (2020) define it as the development of new skills, capacities, and competences, as well as the sharing of this knowledge across organizational members.

Organizational Learning

Organizational learning is the way toward making, hold, and moving learning inside an organization. An organization improves after some time as it adds experience (Namada, 2018). From this experience, it can make learning. This knowledge is broad, encompassing any topic that might benefit a company. Models, on the other hand, may include strategies for increasing generation production or establishing beneficial speculator relationships (Thong, Chau, and Tam, 2019). Learning takes place in four distinct units: individual, group, organizational, and inter-organizational. Expectations to absorb information are a connection that emerges as a company offers a larger degree of an item or service, increasing productivity, efficiency, dependability, and production quality with declining returns. Learning curves vary according to organizational learning rates. Organizational learning rates are affected by individual proficiency, improvements in an organization's technology, and improvements in the structures, routines, and methods of coordination (Fernández-Mesa and

Alegre, 2015). The most common way to measure organizational learning is a learning curve. In addition, learning curves are a relationship showing how as an organization produces more of a product or service, it increases the aforementioned productivity, efficiency, reliability as well as quality of production with diminishing returns (Majdi, 2020). Learning curves vary because of organizational learning rates.

Knowledge Sharing

When the organization grows, moves to multiple sites and creates new subgroups within the same departments, its ability to share knowledge significantly decreases. In smaller, less bureaucratic, less formal organizations with flatter organizational structure and innovative culture, the teams collaborate more efficiently and tend to form various communication flows that support knowledge sharing phenomenon (Chase, 2019). On the other hand, small firms sometimes do not have properly developed strategies concentrated on knowledge transfers. In smaller enterprises it happens, that employees are not aware of the value of their knowledge and they do not have well-organized planning or controlling systems (Chiu, Hsu and Wang, 2006). Smaller organizations do not usually have technologically advanced tools to support their knowledge transfer successfully, especially between departments. Close relations between team members can conduce to creating a social Xie, Zou, & Qi, (2018). Although group cohesiveness can affect positively relations between team members, too tight bonds inside one group can interrupt contact with other departments (Xie, Zou, & Qi, 2018). The following phenomenon may constitute the consequence of the already mentioned social comparison and social categorization process. Strong immersion in a group atmosphere, norms and habits can result in developing not invented here syndrome (NIH). People tend to see the ingroup in more positive terms than they perceive the outgroup, which could be the result of ethnocentrism and bias effect (Boateng & Agyemang,, 2015). Members identifying strongly with their teams usually may be sceptical towards external knowledge.

Knowledge Application

Boateng and Agyemang (2015) define knowledge application as procedures inside organizations that allow them to apply and exploit information in ways that enhance operations, produce new products, and create new knowledge assets. Organizations can find the source of competitive advantage by providing knowledge integration strategies to tackle organizational challenges (Shin et al., 2001). This is one of the most essential parts of knowledge management since the primary purpose of KM is to guarantee that accessible knowledge is used to benefit an organization. Research data demonstrates that when information is properly implemented, it decreases costs and promotes organisational efficiency (Allameh, Zare, and Davoodi, 2011). Knowledge application (KA) is fundamental to knowledge management because it makes knowledge more active and relevant in the generation of company value (Choi, Lee, and Yoo, 2010). Because knowledge is tacit and sticky, the KBV contends that its value comes from its application (Jugend, da Silva, Oprime, and Pimenta, 2015). When businesses use relevant information appropriately, they limit the possibility of making mistakes, eliminate redundancy, boost efficiency, and continually transfer their organizational expertise into embodied goods (Chen and Huang, 2009). KA reacts to various forms of knowledge accessible within an organization and utilizes knowledge that has been developed and shared (Shujahat et al., 2017). Shujahat et al. (2017) points out that KA is more important than other processes such as created knowledge or shared knowledge because knowledge is of no importance until it is applied. Stankovi´c, and Mici´c, (2018) observes that KA enables organisational members to maximise desired outcomes. Whilst past research either neglects KA orexamine KA as having a direct association with innovation performance (Carrera, Brown, Brody, and Morello-Frosch, (2018), this study argues that KA can mediate the relationship

between other KM practices (generation, diffusion and storage) and firm innovation. This means that knowledge generation and diffusion cannot be effective if they are not applied to deliver goods and services and solve problems effectively (Jugend et al., 2015).

Work Team Cohesion

According to Markova and Perry (2014), group cohesiveness has traditionally been researched as a core variable to characterize interactions in small groups and is commonly thought of as a unitary entity. Most formulations conceptually mirror the original idea that cohesiveness is the entire field forces that operate on individuals to keep them in the group (Mardani, Nikoosokhan, Moradi, and Doustar, 2018). Although you can see the trend leaning towards these concepts of cohesion, Mardani, A., Nikoosokhan, Moradi, and Doustar, (2018) also break this idea down and outline the following: “researchers have also argued that cohesion is conceptually different at the individual and group levels. At the individual level, it was defined as individual perceptions of cohesion as the notion of attraction to a group. Towards performance promotion, Kifordu, (2024). At the group level, it was defined as aggregate group cohesion as the members of a shared perception of closeness and unity.

Structure and Focus

Conceptual framework of variables

Figure 2.1 shows an illustration of how the variables of knowledge management influence work-team cohesion.

Source: Researchers Model (2024)

There above framework showed the link between knowledge management and work-team cohesion. An organization improves its work team cohesion over time as it gains experience. Consequently, it can create knowledge. Examples may include ways to increase production efficiency when work team cohesion is improved or to develop beneficial investor relations (Argote, 2012). Organizational learning is a function of experience within an organization besides allows the organization to stay competitive in an ever-changing environment (Majdi, 2020). Knowledge-sharing behaviour has a significant influence on team cohesion, working creativity, group performance, and the knowledge-integration process (Obrenovic, Obrenovic and Hudaykulov, 2015). The sharing of tacit and explicit knowledge leads to innovative ideas (Jackson and Knight, 2006) and improves task efficiency and organizational performance (Adenfelt, 2010).

Theoretical Paradigm

Resource-Based View of the Firm

The study was anchored on the resource-based view theory, a widely referenced theory in strategic management propounded in 1984 by Birger Wernerfelt. Wernerfelt describes a firm as a bundle of resources and attributes superior performance to ownership and control of unique bundles of resources that have the potential to create sustainable competitive advantage for any firm (Gaya, Struwig and Smith, 2013). The resource-based view (RBV)

perceives a firm as an aggregation of resources which are translated by management into strengths and weaknesses of the firm. It assumes that organizations must be successful in obtaining and managing valued resources to be effective. In the resource-based perspective, organizational effectiveness is defined as the ability of the organization in either absolute or relative terms, to obtain scarce and valued resources and successfully integrate and manage such resources (Dess, Lumpkin, Eisner, Lumpkin and McNamara, 2012). This study agrees with the above theory by suggesting that knowledge management, a resource in work-team cohesion influences quality and output in measurable terms.

Empirical Reviews

Ehsan and Masoomeh (2019) examined the knowledge management effect on the performance rate of employees in Iran. The statistical population of this study consisted of all employees of Auxin Steel Company and 380 subjects were chosen at random. The study's findings revealed that employees who are familiar with knowledge management components have more access to these components, which improves their performance. This study seeks to determine if knowledge management has an influence on employee performance or not. The findings revealed that knowledge management applications are an essential component of businesses, and their implementation boosts employee knowledge and information, hence increasing organizational productivity.

Andrea, Filippo, Giulio, and Alessio (2020) investigated the link between knowledge management (KM), performance measurement systems (PMSs), and the economic sustainability of small and medium-sized firms (SMEs) in knowledge-intensive industries. According to the research, SMEs are frequently characterized by unstructured KM methods and limited PMS adoption, while also experiencing low profitability and financial concerns. Using the knowledge-based perspective of the company and the contingency theory of PMSs, we investigated the influence of two distinct KM techniques (extraction and exploration) on SMEs' economic sustainability, as well as the moderating effect of PMS use (diagnostic and interactive). Through an ordinary least squares (OLS) regression of data collected for 219 Italian medium firms operating in knowledge-intensive sectors, this study provides evidence on how a specific KM approach supports the SME economic sustainability and how a consistent implementation and use of PMS amplify the relationship between KM and economic sustainability. Data analysis confirms the relevance of some key concepts of the knowledge-based view of the firm, especially the positive impact of the KM exploration approach on economic sustainability. Additionally, the paper extends empirical evidence for the PMS moderating effect on the KM–performance relationship. Moreover, the findings lead to some managerial implications, especially they encourage SME entrepreneurs and managers to design a coherent KM approach and to implement an adequate PMS to support economic sustainability.

Kavali'c, Nikoli'c, Radosav, Stanislavljev, and Pe'cujlija (2021) studied the elements that impact the efficacy and efficiency of knowledge management applications in transitional situations. The study's data came from a poll of 520 respondents, who were managers at different levels in Serbian manufacturing businesses. A t-test was performed in many versions. The t-test analysis was performed on the average assessments of knowledge management dimensions, as well as particular control variables. The findings show that knowledge management characteristics differ across local and international firms, and that their influence varies throughout organizational levels. Financial performance (profitability, sales growth, asset growth, market share, competitive position in a certain sector, productivity, and wages) was shown to be an accurate predictor of knowledge management success. It is clear that knowledge management aspects play an essential role in transition nations, and good knowledge management is critical to an organization's competitive sustainability.

Review Summary

Having established the conceptual framework, we first focused the review on identifying both variables interrelated with significant influence. The components of knowledge management such as organizational learning, knowledge sharing, knowledge application, and intellectual capital have an impact on work team cohesion. There is a link between knowledge management dimensions and work-team cohesion. An organization improves its work team cohesion over time as it gains experience through organizational learning. Majdi (2020) found that Organizational learning is a function of experience within an organization besides allowing the organization to stay competitive in an ever-changing environment.

Obrenovic, Obrenovic, and Hudaykulov (2015) discovered that information-sharing behaviour has a substantial impact on team cohesiveness, working creativity, group performance, and knowledge integration. Sharing tacit and explicit information generates novel ideas (Jackson and Knight, 2006) and enhances work efficiency and organizational performance (Adenfelt, 2010). When an organization expands, relocates to numerous places, and forms new subgroups within the same divisions, its capacity to exchange information suffers dramatically. Chase (2019) discovered that in smaller, less bureaucratic, less formal firms with a flatter organizational structure and an inventive culture, teams work more efficiently and establish diverse communication channels that promote the knowledge-sharing phenomena.

On the other hand, small firms sometimes do not have properly developed strategies concentrated on knowledge transfers. In smaller enterprises it happens, that employees are not aware of the value of their knowledge and they do not have well-organized planning or controlling systems (Chiu, Hsu and Wang, 2006).

Previous studies showed that knowledge application is a fundamental success factor for the development of new products and a key facilitator of innovation, work team cohesion and performance (Hamdoun et al., 2018; Mardani, Nikoosokhan, Moradi and Doustar, 2018).Bature, Sallehuddin and Hin (2018) asserted that nowadays, the behaviour of companies is based on knowledge that must be understood by the members of the organization as an intellectual capital that needs to be adopted to solve problems of limited resources and match the needs of the market. Obeidat, Abualoush, Irtaimah, Khaddam and Bataineh, (2018) discovered that intellectual capital has become very important element for the success of organizations in a complex environment in a knowledge era. In addition, intellectual capital is the relevant source of the competitive advantage of firms (Obeidat et al., 2018), leading to enhanced capacity for innovation, work team cohesion and firm performance.

Interventions

The review focused on team cohesiveness in the workplace, including organizational learning, information exchange, and implementation. The scientific foundation for the majority of the components that might impact team processes was well established. However, team development was a topic with a lot of theory but little facts; this has not altered in the ensuing years. Across the themes, there is a significant quantity of practical information. The analysis presented several specific, focused recommendations for how these intervention levers may be utilized to promote team cohesiveness across a variety of companies.

Impact and Contributions

As previously stated, the review's primary contribution was to develop a set of evidence-based conclusions and recommendations about "what we know, what we think we know, and what we need to know to improve work cohesiveness using knowledge management amongst teams" (Zheng, Yang, & McLean, 2010). We were able to go beyond where most reviews end by filtering the literature to focus on well-developed areas and those that

showed promise, calibrating our conclusions to match the weight of the evidence, and generating actionable targets for application.

More study is always ideal to go deeper into subtlety, but there is a science of work cohesion, and its conclusions are broadly applicable. The review made those scientific discoveries more apparent and accessible, and I believe that part of knowing the dimensions of knowledge contributed to teamwork cohesion. The reviews and preceding studies supported this stance as a more general measure of impact on succession and knowledge sharing Kifordu, (2024).

Another area of contribution is the degree to which this qualitative assessment spreads to other fields. Articles that are referenced outside of their original disciplinary area have more influence since they expand and transfer science into other fields. According to research, almost all areas of modern science are becoming more team-based (rather than solitary investigators). Furthermore, the most influential science of knowledge management transforms a fresh concept from another subject into a mature path of investigation (Yiu, & Law 2014).

A third facet of impact and contribution is the degree to which a publication inspires future study. It is difficult to describe extremely precise impacts that may be traced back to the review. Authors frequently utilize references to detailed evaluations as a seasoning for broad and general arguments. Furthermore, the precise recommendations we gave were based on the research and included specific references.

Conclusion

The study concluded that knowledge management has an impact on work-team cohesion. Organizational learning influences work-team cohesion. Organizational learning is a process improvement that can increase efficiency, accuracy, work team cohesion and profits. Moreover, organizational learning is an aspect of organizations and a subfield of organizational studies. Thus, as an aspect of an organization, organizational learning remains the process of creating, retaining, as well as transferring knowledge. Individuals' knowledge facilitates learning within the organization if it is transferred. Individuals may withhold the organization's knowledge. The knowledge that is embedded in the organization, in addition, to its individuals, can be retained.

Knowledge sharing affects work-team cohesion. Smaller organizations do not usually have technologically advanced tools to support their knowledge transfer successfully, especially between departments. Close relations between team members can conduce to creating social networks and developing a sense of trust in people, which can result in an effective knowledge-sharing style. Also, interpersonal skills and outgoing posture can improve knowledge flow efficiency in an organization, especially when the group structure is not associated with a strong hierarchy or strictly formal.

Knowledge application influences work-team cohesiveness. Organizations may accelerate the creation of new products, improve work-team cohesiveness, and improve administrative and technological system processing by using knowledge. When information is efficiently utilized, it lowers costs, improves work team cohesiveness, and promotes organizational efficiency. Organisations may find the source of competitive advantage by providing knowledge integration strategies to solve organizational difficulties.

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